

Ultrasonic velocity and allied properties of manganese, cobalt and copper soaps in non-aqueous medium

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Abstract : The ultrasonic velocity of the solution of manganese, cobalt and copper soaps (caprate, laurate and myristate) were carried out in a mixture of benzene and methanol (50% v/v) at a constant temperature. The data have been used to evaluate the critical micelle concentration (CMC) and to study the soap-soap and soap-solvent interactions. The various acoustic parameters, viz. adiabatic compressibility, intermolecular free length, apparent molar compressibility, specific acoustic impedance, available volume and relative association were evaluated. The results confirm that there is a significant interaction between the soap and solvent molecules.

Keywords : Ultrasonics, manganese, copper, cobalt.

In the recent years there has been considerable progress in the determination of thermodynamic, rheological and acoustical properties of metallic soaps from speed, density and viscosity measurements. The physico-chemical characteristics of metal soaps can be controlled up to an extent by the method and conditions of their preparation and so the studies of metal soap is of great significance as these soaps are used in various industries. The ultrasonic velocity technique has been used for studying solute-solvent interaction in a number of systems including organic liquid and dilute solutions in organic acids¹. The propagation of ultrasonic waves and the measurement of their velocity have been used to determine the nature of molecular interaction in the systems.

The present work has been initiated with a view to determine the critical micelle concentration, and to study the soap-solvent interactions and various acoustic parameters. The efforts have also been made to investigate the effect of concentration on the chain length of metal soap and atomic number of metal ion present.

Preparation of metal soaps :

Potassium soaps (caprate, laurate and myristate) were prepared by refluxing equivalent amounts of corresponding fatty acid and potassium hydroxide solution on a water bath for 6–8 h. The metal soaps were prepared by direct metathesis of the corresponding potassium soap (caprate, laurate and myristate) with slight excess of the solution of metal acetate (manganese acetate, cobalt acetate and copper acetate) at 50–55 °C under vigorous stirring. The metal soaps thus obtained were first dried in

an air oven and the final drying of the soaps was carried out under reduced pressure. The purity of the soap was confirmed by the determination of their melting points and infrared spectra.

Melting points : Manganese caprate – 102 °C, manganese laurate – 108 °C, manganese myristate – 112 °C, cobalt caprate – 108 °C, cobalt laurate – 112 °C, cobalt myristate – 116 °C, copper caprate – 115 °C, copper laurate – 119 °C and copper myristate – 126 °C.

Preparation of soaps solution :

The calculated amount of metal soap was weighed in a standard flask and the solution was made up by adding required amount of solvent mixture. In this way, a number of solutions containing different concentration of metal soaps in a mixture of benzene and methanol (50% v/v) were prepared.

Ultrasonic velocity measurements : Ultrasonic velocity measurements were taken by using a multifrequency ultrasonic interferometer (M-83, Mittal Enterprises, New Delhi) at a frequency of 1 MHz at a constant temperature (40 ± 0.05 °K). The uncertainty of velocity measurements was 0.2%. The densities of solvent and the solution were measured with a dilatometer.

Calculation : The various acoustic parameters such as adiabatic compressibility, β , intermolecular free length, L_f^2 , specific acoustic impedance, Z , apparent molar compressibility, ϕ_k and available volume, V_a were calculated using the following relationships.

Adiabatic compressibility, $\beta = v^{-2}p^{-1}$

Intermolecular free length, $L_f = (\beta/K)^{1/2}$

Specific acoustic impedance, $Z = v \cdot \rho$

Apparent molar compressibility,

$$\phi_k' = \frac{1000}{C\rho_0}(\rho_0\beta - \rho\beta_0) + \frac{M\beta_0}{\rho_0}$$

Available volume, $V_a = \bar{V}(1 - v/v_\alpha)$

$$\text{Relative association, } R_A = \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \right) \left(\frac{v_0}{v} \right)$$

where v , v_0 ; ρ , ρ_0 ; β , β_0 and \bar{V} , \bar{V}_0 are the ultrasonic velocity, density, adiabatic compressibility and molar volume of the solute and solvent respectively, n , n_0 and M , M_0 are the number of moles and molecular weight of solute and solvent respectively, K and C are the temperature dependent Jacobson's constant² and concentration in mol L^{-1} , respectively.

Results and discussion

Density : The density, ρ of the solutions of manganese, cobalt and copper soaps of caprate, laurate and myristate in a mixture of 50% benzene and 50% methanol (v/v) increases first slowly and then rapidly with increasing soap concentration. The plots of density, ρ vs soap concentration, C are characterised by an intersection of two straight lines at a definite soap concentration, which corresponds to the CMC of the soap. The results show that the CMC value decreases with increasing chain length of the soap molecules and with increasing atomic number of metal ion. The plots of the density, ρ vs soap concentration, C below the CMC have been extrapolated to zero soap concentration and extrapolated values of the density, ρ_0 are in agreement with the experimental values of the density 0.8047 of pure solvent mixture. It is therefore, concluded that the soap molecules do not show appreciable aggregation below the CMC whereas there is a marked change in the aggregation of the soap molecules at this definite soap concentration.

Ultrasonic velocity : The ultrasonic velocity v , of manganese, cobalt and copper soap (caprate, laurate and myristate) solutions increases with the increasing concentration, chain length of the soap and with increasing the atomic number of the metal ion soap content. The variation of velocity, v with concentration, C , in solutions depends on the concentration derivatives of density, ρ and adiabatic compressibility, β .

$$\frac{dv}{dc} = \frac{-v}{2} \left[\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{d\rho}{dc} + \frac{1}{\beta} \frac{d\beta}{dc} \right]$$

The results show that the density increases while the adiabatic compressibility decreases with increasing soap concentration. Thus the quantity, $d\rho/dc$ is positive while $d\beta/dc$ is negative.

Since the values of $[(1/\beta) \cdot (d\beta/dc)]$ are larger than the values of $[(1/\rho) \cdot (d\rho/dc)]$ for these soap solutions, the concentration derivative of velocity, dv/dc is positive i.e. the ultrasonic velocity increases with increasing soap concentration. These results are in agreement with the results of other workers reported for electrolytic solutions indicating that these soaps behave as simple electrolytes in dilute solution in the benzene-methanol mixture (50 : 50 v/v).

The plots of ultrasonic velocity vs soap concentration for solutions (Fig. 1) of manganese, cobalt and copper soaps (caprate, laurate and myristate) in benzene-metha-

Fig. 1. Ultrasonic velocity vs concentration : (O) caprate, (●) laurate, (Δ) myristate.

Table 1. Extrapolated and experimental values of ultrasonic velocity, CMC and other parameters of metal soaps at 40 ± 0.05 °C

Sl. no.	Metal soaps	CMC $\times 10^3$ (mol L ⁻¹)			G (m s ⁻¹ C mol ⁻¹ dm ³)	Ultrasonic velocity, V_0		Adiabatic compressibility, β_0	
		From ultrasonic velocity measurement	From conductivity measurement	From viscosity measurement		Extra-polated	Experi-mental	Extra-polated	Experi-mental
1.	Manganese caprate	0.0138	0.0138	0.117	800.0	1100.2	1101.0	10.266	10.251
2.	Manganese laurate	0.0126	0.0126	0.112	1076.0	1100.4	1101.0	10.262	10.251
3.	Manganese myristate	0.0118	0.0118	0.108	1200.0	1101.2	1101.0	10.247	10.251
4.	Cobalt caprate	0.0126	0.0126	0.112	866.6	1101.2	1101.0	10.247	10.251
5.	Cobalt laurate	0.0118	0.0118	0.106	1111.1	1101.4	1101.0	10.244	10.251
6.	Cobalt myristate	0.0108	0.0108	0.103	1250.0	1102.0	1101.0	10.232	10.251
7.	Copper caprate	0.0114	0.0114	0.106	1000.0	1102.0	1101.0	10.232	10.251
8.	Copper laurate	0.0106	0.0108	0.102	1222.2	1102.2	1101.0	10.229	10.251
9.	Copper myristate	0.0092	0.0092	0.095	1500.0	1102.4	1101.2	10.225	10.251

nol mixture show a break at a definite soap concentration which corresponds to the CMC of the soap. The values of CMC decreases with increasing chain length of the soap molecules and atomic number of the metal ion are recorded in Table 1.

The extrapolated values of velocity, v_0 for caprate, laurate and myristate for manganese, cobalt, and copper soaps (Table 1) are in close agreement with the experimental value of velocity in the solvent mixture indicating that the soap molecules do not aggregate up to appreciable extent below the CMC.

The variation of ultrasonic velocity, v with soap concentration C , follows the relationship

$$v = v_0 + GC$$

where v_0 is the ultrasonic velocity in pure solvent and G is Garnsey's constant³. The value of Garnsey's constant for metal soap in benzene-methanol mixture has been calculated from the slope of the plots of v vs C . The calculated value of Garnsey's constant increases with increasing chain length of soap molecule and with the atomic number of the metal ion. The values of Garnsey's constants, G , are shown in Table 1.

The plots of adiabatic compressibility, β vs soap concentration, C indicate a break at definite soap concentration which corresponds to the CMC of manganese, cobalt and copper soaps. The extrapolated values of the solvent mixture, β_0 are in close agreement with the experimental value of the adiabatic compressibility (Table 1).

The intermolecular free length, L_f decreases while specific acoustic impedance, Z , increases with increasing soap concentration indicating that there is significant in-

teraction between the soap and solvent molecules which considerably affect the structure arrangement. The increase in the value of Z with increasing C can be explained on the basis of lyophobic interaction between soap and solvent molecules which increases the intermolecular distance. The plot of L_f vs C and Z vs C are characterized by the intersection of the two lines at definite soap concentration which corresponds to the CMC of the soaps and the extrapolated values of intermolecular free length L_f^0 and specific acoustic impedance (Z^0) are in good agreement with the values for the solvent mixture. This again confirms the fact that the soap molecules do not aggregate to an appreciable extent below the CMC whereas there is a marked change in aggregation at the CMC. The values of CMC are in agreement with the value obtained from other parameters.

The results of adiabatic compressibility have been explained in term of Bachem's⁴ equation

$$\beta = \beta_0 + AC + BC^{3/2}$$

where A and B are constants, C is the molar concentration and β and β_0 are the adiabatic compressibility of the solutions and solvent, respectively. The plots of $(\beta - \beta_0)/C$ vs $C^{1/2}$ are linear. The intercept and slope of the plots have been used to obtain the values of constant A and B (Table 2).

The values of apparent molar compressibility, ϕ_k increases with increasing soap concentration and chain length of the soap molecule. It follows from Debye-Hückel's theory that the apparent molar compressibility, ϕ_k is related to the soap concentration, C , by the relationship.

$$\phi_k = \phi_k^0 + S_k C^{1/2}$$

Table 2. Values of constant A and B as obtained from the plots of $\beta - \beta_0/C$ vs \sqrt{C} and values of constant ϕ_k^0 and S_k obtained

Sl. no.	Metal soaps	from plots of ϕ_k vs \sqrt{C}			
		$A \times 10^{10}$ $m^2 N^{-1}$ $mol^{-1} L$	$B \times 10^{10}$ $m^2 N^{-1}$ $mol^{-2} L^2$	$\phi_k \times 10^{-6}$ $m^5 N^{-1} kg^{-1}$ mol^{-1}	$S_k \times 10^6$ $m^5 N^{-1} kg^{-1}$ $mol^{-2} L$
1.	Manganese caprate	-60.4	384.60	12.60	100.00
2.	Cobalt caprate	-50.8	416.66	11.8	80.00
3.	Copper caprate	-60.4	500.00	13.8	60.00
4.	Manganese laurate	-70.1	466.66	13.00	139.00
5.	Cobalt laurate	-70.4	533.33	12.6	107.62
6.	Copper laurate	-80.5	615.38	15.40	80.00
7.	Manganese myristate	-90.8	666.66	17.00	160.00
8.	Cobalt myristate	-80.1	700.00	11.4	133.00
9.	Copper myrsitate	-120.0	933.33	25.8	120.00

where ϕ_k^0 and S_k are the limiting apparent molar compressibility and a constant. The plot of ϕ_k vs \sqrt{C} exhibits a break at a concentration which corresponds to the CMC of metal soaps. The intercept and slope of the plots have been used to obtain value of ϕ_k^0 and constant S_k , respectively for caprate, laurate and myristate of Mn, Co and Cu soaps (Table 1). The results are in agreement with the results reported by Masson for electrolytic solutions.

The values of available volume V_a and relative association R_A decrease with increasing soap concentration. The plots of V_a and R_A vs soap concentration, C are characterised by a break at the CMC. The ultrasonic velocity results show that manganese, cobalt and copper soaps behave as a simple electrolyte in solutions. The results confirm that there is a significant interaction between the soap and solvent molecule in dilute solutions and the soap molecule do not aggregate appreciably below the CMC. The CMC values are in agreement with the values obtained from other parameters.

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